

Science Europe Reaction

To the Political Partial Agreement on Horizon Europe: A Good Deal but is there a Supporting Budget?

Brussels, 17 April 2019

Science Europe welcomes the Political Partial Agreement on Horizon Europe, the next Framework Programme for research and innovation (R&I), previously approved by the Council and voted on today in plenary by the European Parliament. Horizon Europe is an ambitious programme, designed to strengthen the European position in the global landscape of R&I and deliver visible impact for society. It is to play a key complementary role to national research funding and demonstrate the value European co-operation can bring.

Science Europe is very pleased to see that excellence remains the core principle of the programme. It also welcomes the increase of the budget earmarked to support low R&I-performing countries to help develop their scientific capacities and resources, and foster their participation in the programme.

These results would not have been possible without the hard work of the European Parliament, especially the rapporteurs Dan Nica and Christian Ehler, Commissioner Carlos Moedas and the staff at Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, and the Council, notably the Austrian and Romanian Presidencies.

“This is great news for the research community”, says Stephan Kuster, Secretary General of Science Europe. “Such an agreement before the European Parliament elections was very much needed to ensure that Horizon Europe will be fully up and running by the end of 2020. Thanks to this agreement, Horizon Europe is set to be the best Framework Programme yet.”

Next Steps

Horizon Europe’s ambitions can only be met with the appropriate funding. Science Europe therefore advises the European Council and the Finance Ministers to grant Horizon Europe a budget of at least €120bn, as requested by the European Parliament, as part of the 2021-2027 Multi-annual Financial Framework negotiations.

Science Europe also urges the EU Institutions to foster, through Horizon Europe, collaboration with strong research performers based in countries that are not EU members. The participation of researchers and innovators from these countries, including Switzerland and potentially a post-Brexit United Kingdom, provides real added value for them and for the EU and should be encouraged.

There is still a long way to go until Horizon Europe is officially launched, and Science Europe looks forward to contributing to the design of the programme implementation. A continued collaboration between the European Commission and the R&I community in general, and Science Europe members in particular, will be essential in the preparation of the strategic plans, the design of the missions, and the definition of partnerships.